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Research Article

ASSESSMENT OF THE FREQUENCY OF PROTEINURIA IN TYPE II DIABETES MELLITUS PATIENTS AT TETTIARY CARE HOSPITAL OF DERA ISMAIL KHAN PAKISTAN

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Abstract:

Objective: Diabetes mellitus (DM) is one of the dangerous disease if left unmanaged ..The objective of the current research is to assess the frequency of proteinuria in type 2 diabetes mellitus people

Methodology: The descriptive cross sectional study was made at teaching hospital of Dera Ismail Khan . Consecutive non probability sampling were used to collect the samples.

Results: The frequencies and percentages for protienuria were recorded in 100 (47.61%). The range of proteinuria was considerably high (47.61%) in the studied sample.

Conclusion: The routine screening for proteinuria is suggested for over all patients, And the patients aged 61-70 y suffered more from proteinuria.

Keywords: Diabetic Nephropathy, Proteinuria, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a clinical syndrome of disordered metabolism and chronic hyperglycemia because of insulin inadequacy, inefficiency or both. [1,2] Diabetes is the untreatable disease but it is not the cause of serious concern because it has been observed that the patients having this problem can still enjoy the pleasant life, the reason is that proper management by means of the food and medicine. That's why the pharmacological and non pharmacological treatments are suggested especially the patients are first asked to concentrate more on the non pharmacological treatments. If the Diabetes is left unmanaged then it can trigger many complications such as . Neuropathy is one of a major complication.¹⁻² The prevalence of diabetes was estimated worldwide to be 2.8% in 2000 and 4.4% in 2030. [3] Diabetes mellitus is increasing at the alarming point and it is said that it is the wake up call for the health professionals of the world to adopt the proper measures to curb this fast increasing disease.[4].The world health organization (WHO) estimates 171 million of patients with diabetes mellitus worldwide in 2002 and is estimated to augment to 366 million cases by 2030. [5-6].

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) is most frequent actually the exact cause of this disease is still based on numerous factors and it is said that obesity is one of the strong cause for the prevalence of this disease. In addition to this various other factors such as zero physical activity, inadequate sleep, improper eating habits and the most strong is the genetics. It is said that this disease is more prevalent among the patients who have the family history . Its better to get the sugar level and HbA1c checked on monthly basis because if this disease diagnosed later it can pose serious threat to the patient [7-8,9].The prevalence of Type 2 more in UK and USA, which increases above 30% risk of life-time in these groups. The overall prevalence of type 2 diabetes within the UK is 4–6%, and the lifetime risk is around 15–20%. [10-11].

Proteinuria is said that, generally > 150–160 mg/24 h in adults. Significant proteinuria is a sign of an underlying kidney abnormality, usually glomerular in

origin when > 1–2 g/d. [5] Proteinuria is better to be checked and managed properly because this is the cause of concern and especially responsible for kidneys dysfunction. [6] The prevalence of microalbuminuria in type2 diabetes patients has been reported to be 36.0 to 48%. [7,8,9] Nephropathy is main complexity which is reported because of the protein excretion in the urine and it is enhancing the arterial BP and therefore it is has been witnessed that it is the problem lying behind the kidneys dysfunction .It is matter of fact that the diabetic patients cant even undergo th kidneys transplantation hence the things should be kept in mind before they get worse . [12-13] The objective of the present study is to have watchdog on the Proteinuria because it is said that it can prove the primary cause for the malfunction of the kidneys and as we know that the kidneys are the vital organs of the body hence if anything wrong happens to the kidneys the life expectancy will be decreased ,So it is the wiser to have the clear picture of the complications associated with the DM and if the complexities are cut in the early stages several other complications can be subsided .

METHODOLOGY:

The descriptive cross sectional research made for the period of 8 months Hospital of Dera Ismail Khan KPK Pakistan . Consecutive non probability sampling was used as the sampling technique .The sample size was taken using the formula = **210** Confidence Interval = 95% Absolute precision = 6.5% Anticipated population proportion = 36.10%.

Inclusion criteria:

All Type 2 diabetes mellitus patients of both gender males and females as per operational definitions.

Exclusion criteria:

Type 2 diabetics undergoing any form of dialysis . Diabetics on insulin therapy. Already diagnosed type I diabetic patients. The above mentioned conditions acts as confounders and if included will introduce bias in study results.

RESULTS:**TABLE 1:****GENDER DISTRIBUTION**

(N=210)

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	146	69.53%
Female	64	30.47%

Table 1 depicts the gender based division of the patients

TABLE 2:
AGE DISTRIBUTION
(N=210)

AGE GROUP	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGES
40-50 Years	69	32.85%
51-60 Years	71	33.80%
61-70 Years	70	33.33%

Table 2 shows the age wise distribution of the study sample

TABLE 3
FREQUENCIES AND PERCENTAGES FOR
PROTEINURIA

(N=210)

PROTEINURIA	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGES
Yes	100	47.61%
No	110	52.38%

table 03 is depicting the frequency of the proteinuria among the patients suffering from Diabetes Mellitus type II.

TABLE NO. 4
STRATIFICATION OF PROTEINURIA WITH RESPECT AGE
(N=210)

AGE	PROTEINURIA	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE	P-VALUE
40-50 Years	Yes	36	17.14%	0.306
	No	33	15.71%	
51-60 Years	Yes	34	16.19%	0.087
	No	37	17.61%	
61-70 Years	Yes	31	14.76%	0.080
	No	39	18.57%	

DISCUSSION:

The age wise distribution in 40-50 years age group was 69 (32.85%), in 51-60 years age group it was 71 (33.80%) while in age group of 61-70 years it was 70 (33.33%) . As per Gender distribution, the frequency of males were recorded as 146 (69.53%) however the frequency of females were 64 (30.47%) The frequencies and percentages for duration diabetes was recorded as 64 (30.47%) were having diabetes for more than 10 years while 146 (69.53%) had diabetes for less than 10 years of depression was recorded as 9 (7.89%) The frequencies and percentages for residential status are 107 (50.95%) were from rural areas and 103 (49.04%) patients were

from urban areas (Table No. 4). The frequencies and percentages for family history of diabetic mellitus was recorded 178 (84.76%) had history of diabetes while 32 (15.32%) patients had no history of diabetes (Table No. 5). The frequencies and percentages for occupation were recorded as 08(03.80%) patients were labourers, 51 (24.28%) patients were Govt servants, 105 (50%) patients were businessmen while 46 (21.90%) patients were house wives (Table No. 6). The frequencies and percentages for glyceemic control were recorded as 35 (16.66%) patients had poor glyceemic control while 175 (83.33%) had good glyceemic control (Table No. 7). Frequencies and percentages for hypertension were recorded as 64

(30.47%) were found hyper tensed while 146 (69.53%) were no hypertensive.

CONCLUSION: The overall prevalence rate of proteinuria was considerably high (47.61%) among the studied diabetic patients. Hence the regular assessment of the . proteinuria is needed because its' better to approach the disorder in the initial stage before it could progress and pose more serious threats .It was observed from the study that the increased excretion of protein in the urine can cause serious problem of nephropathy and it can be fatal if left unmanaged .

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